

NOTES

Complexes of Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper- and Zinc-(II) with Chlorpheniramine Maleate. A Physicochemical Study

PRAMILA SINGH* and M. S. KACHHAWAHA

Department of Chemistry,
Dr. Hari Singh Gour Vishwavidyalaya, Sagar-470 003

Manuscript received 1 August 1988, revised 26 October 1989,
accepted 6 December 1989

THE present communication describes the preparation and characterisation of chlorpheniramine maleate complexes with Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with the aid of analytical, conductance, magnetic, molecular weight, ir and electronic spectral data.

Experimental

Metal salts used were of AnalaR grade. Chlorpheniramine maleate (I.D.P.L.) was used as such. The following general procedure was adopted for the preparation of the complexes. Concentrated aqueous solution of the ligand in slight excess over the stoichiometric M : L ratio of 1 : 2 was added slowly with constant stirring to an acidic aqueous metal ion solution. The pH was adjusted to about 6 by adding dilute ammonia. The mixture was refluxed for 1 h on a water-bath. The resulting solid was repeatedly washed with warm distilled water and dried first over anhydrous CaCl_2 and then at 110° for about 1 h. The complexes were found to be insoluble in most of the organic solvents but soluble in basic solvents like DMF and pyridine. All the complexes were stable and non-hygroscopic.

The analytical data of the complexes were obtained from Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow. The metal content of the complexes was determined by standard procedures¹. Electronic spectra (DMF) were recorded on a EV-700-22 spectrophotometer and ir spectra on Perkin-Elmer 577 and 621 spectrophotometers. Molar conductance was determined

in DMF using 10^{-3} M solution of the complexes. Molecular weight determination of the complexes were carried out by the Rast method using diphenyl as the solvent. The results are presented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Low molar conductances ($2.5-9.2 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) of the complexes indicate their non-electrolytic nature which implies that the anions are present inside the coordination sphere.

The electronic spectra of the complexes showed two maxima at 38168 cm^{-1} which may be due to $\pi-\pi^*$ transition while the other band at 26666 cm^{-1} may be assigned to ligand-metal charge transfer. Electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complex showed two bands—the one near 20408 cm^{-1} corresponds to transition ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ and the second broad asymmetric band around 14285 cm^{-1} assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ transition—indicating distortion from a regular octahedral structure²⁻⁴. The Ni^{II} complex showed a broad and asymmetric band at $19230-11235 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be assigned to a combination of three transitions, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$. This result together with the magnetic moment value suggest an octahedral geometry for the Ni^{II} complex⁵. In the visible region, three transitions, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ are expected for the Cu^{II} complexes. They are very close in energy and often give rise to one broad band envelop. In the present case a broad band near 17857 cm^{-1} has been observed. This displacement to lower wavelength indicates formation of stronger M-N bond. On the basis of visible spectra, distorted octahedral geometry can be assigned to the Cu^{II} complex.

The band observed in the regions $3083-2995$ and $2940-2852 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ir spectra of the ligand and the complexes have been assigned to C-H pyridine and benzene ring⁶. The band

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Mol. weight Found/(Calcd.)	Decomp. temp. °C	μ_{eff} ** B.M.
		M	N	Cl			
[Co(Chlorph) ₂ Cl ₂]	Bluish green	8.73 (8.67)	8.51 (8.24)	20.76 (20.89)	669.14 (679.53)	265	4.8
[Ni(Chlorph) ₂ Cl ₂]	Green	8.77 (8.64)	8.20 (8.24)	20.98 (20.90)	671.79 (679.31)	270	3.28
[Cu(Chlorph) ₂ Cl ₂]	Greenish grey	9.35 (9.28)	8.11 (8.18)	20.85 (20.75)	675.01 (684.14)	272	1.8
[Zn(Chlorph) ₂ Cl ₂]	Dull white	9.63 (9.52)	8.11 (8.16)	20.60 (20.70)	670.25 (685.97)	252	—

*Chlorph = $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{19}\text{ClN}_2$. **At 301 K.

at 1190 cm^{-1} may be assigned to tertiary amino group of dimethyl moiety⁷. This band was shifted to 1100 , 1100 , 1110 and 1110 cm^{-1} for the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes respectively. This suggests the involvement of tertiary nitrogen atom of the group in complexation. Since the bands due to $\text{C}=\text{C}$ and $\text{C}=\text{N}$ mixed stretching vibrations found in the ligand at 1585 and 1550 cm^{-1} were shifted in the complexes near 1525 and 1505 cm^{-1} , the nitrogen atom of pyridine ring is also involved in the complexation^{8,9}. The sharp band at 1705 cm^{-1} in spectra of the ligand may be due to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ of maleate ion. It was reported⁶ that some bands observed in the region $1160-1060\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are due to pyridine vibrations. In the present case similar bands were observed in the ligand and the complexes but they were of quite weak intensity. The band near 780 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the ligand and the complexes has been assigned to $\nu_{\text{C-Cl}}$ ⁶. The band near 475 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the complexes may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ ^{10,11}. The weak bands at 384 , 380 , 375 and 250 cm^{-1} in the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes respectively may be assigned to coordinated N atom of pyridine ring. The bands at $300-220\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the complexes may be assigned to $\text{M}-\text{Cl}$ ^{12,13}.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (P. S.) is grateful to I.C.M.R., New Delhi, for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship and also grateful to Prof. S. P. Banerjee, Head, Department of Chemistry for facilities.

References

1. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis Including Instrumental Analysis", ELBS, London, 1978, pp. 321, 322, 330, 433, 435.
2. F. A. COTTON, D. M. L. GOODGAME and M. GOODGAME, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4690.
3. F. M. DUNN, "The Visible and Ultraviolet Spectra of Complex Compounds in Modern Coordination Chemistry", eds. J. LEWIS and R. G. WILKINS, Interscience, New York, 1960, p. 290.
4. Y. TANABE and S. SUGANO, *J. Phys. Soc. Jpn.*, 1954, **9**, 753.
5. P. L. MOURYA, B. V. AGARWALA and A. K. DEY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, **19**, 807.
6. L. J. BRILLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Methuen, London, 1958.
7. N. B. COLTHUP, *J. Opt. Soc. Am.*, 1950, **40**, 397.
8. D. M. ADAMS, "Metal Ligand and Related Vibrations", Arnold, London, 1957.
9. L. MARION, D. A. RAMSAY and R. N. JONES, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **13**, 305.
10. M. A. ALI and S. E. LIVINGSTONE, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1976, **13**, 101.
11. R. A. CONDRADE and K. NAKAMOTO, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1964, **42**, 2590.
12. D. M. ADAMS, J. CHATT, J. M. DAVIDSON and J. GERRATT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 2189.
13. G. POSTMUS, J. R. FERRARO, A. QUATTROCHI, K. SHOBATAKE and K. NAKAMOTO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, **8**, 1851.

Studies on Coordination Polymers. Part-II.

Polymeric Complexes of Di(*o*-aminophenyl)disulphide with Nickel(II), Cobalt(II), Manganese(II) and Chromium(III)

(Mrs.) P. R. SHUKLA*, NIHAL AHMAD

and

B. B. AWASTHI

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University, Lucknow-226 007

Manuscript received 6 February 1989, revised 7 December 1989, accepted 21 December 1989

SOME polymeric complexes in which nitrogen and sulphur donor atoms are present, have been studied in this laboratory¹. The present communication records the synthesis and characterisation of a tetradentate ligand di(*o*-aminophenyl)disulphide (1) containing two sulphur and two amino groups and its complexes with Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Mn^{II} and Cr^{III} .

1

Experimental

o-Nitrobenzenethiol (NBT): A mixture of *o*-nitrochlorobenzene (15.8 g, 0.1 mol) and thiourea (7.8 g, 0.1 mol) in ethanol was refluxed till all the thiourea had dissolved. The solution was distilled under reduced pressure and the resulting solid was recrystallised using petroleum ether-ethanol mixture, dried and analysed (Table 1).

Di(*o*-nitrophenyl)disulphide (DNPS): A mixture of *o*-nitrobenzenethiol (15.6 g, 0.01 mol), 1N NaOH (140 ml) and iodine (12.6 g) was refluxed for 6 h. Air was then bubbled through the solution for 4 h and the resulting yellow solid was recrystallised and analysed (Table 1).

Di(*o*-aminophenyl)disulphide (DAPS): DNPS (6.16 g) and Raney nickel (0.5 g) were suspended in methanol and hydrazine hydrate (~5 ml) was added dropwise with refluxing and constant stirring. On cooling the resulting brown solid was crystallised from acetone and analysed (Table 1).

Preparation of metal complexes: To a suspension of appropriate metal salt (0.01 mol) in xylene (50 ml), the ligand DAPS (2.48 g, 0.01 mol) was added and the solution was refluxed for 10-14 h. The solvent was then distilled off and the resulting solid was crystallised from petroleum ether, dried and analysed (Table 2).

Molar conductance (DMSO), ir spectra, magnetic susceptibility and electronic spectra were explored to characterise the complexes. Solubility